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QUANTIFICATION OF SMOKING EFFECTS ON MICROBIAL DIVERSITY OF ORAL AND RESPIRATORY TRACT

Pallavi Singh*, Ananya Singh, Sana Zahid, Ravi Kumar, Deeksha Savita, Ridhima Jain

*Department of Biotechnology,
IILM Academy of Higher Learning, Gr. Noida(U.P), India

ABSTRACT

Cigarette smokers have an increased risk of infections and diseases involving the respiratory tract. Cigarette smoke damages the lining of the airways and makes the lungs more prone to infections. Tobacco smoking has been correlated with many oral mucosal abnormalities and increased colonization with candida species. Investigative research study was carried to see the effect of tobacco smoking on the oral and respiratory tract micro flora. Sputum and Saliva samples were collected from 30 subjects consisting of 15 smokers and 15 non smokers in the age group 20- 38 yrs. Subjects selected in this study were Engineering students and Labourers working in construction industries. Microbial profile from sputum and saliva was examined. Samples were cultured overnight after serial dilution and spread plated on various media i.e Nutrient Agar, Mannitol Agar, Sabouraud's Dextrose Agar and Luria Agar. Bacteria and fungus obtained from these media were further examined using Gram staining technique and characterised on the basis of morphological characteristics. The further classification of bacteria & fungus was done using selective and differential media for each. Candida species were isolated using the oral rinse technique. Analysis of results has shown significantly higher number of E.coli, Streptococcus Aureus and Candida species in sample of smokers as compared to Nonsmokers.

Keywords: Tobacco Smoking, Gram Staining, Selective media, Streptococcus, Candida species

INRODUCTION

With there being over 1 billion adult smokers worldwide smoking-related health hazards presents a global public health issue. cigarette smokers in addition to having a high predisposition to develop cancer of the respiratory and gastrointestinal epithelium have tendencies to develop gingival infection occurs as a result of complex interaction of the host bacteria and the short or long term effects of tobacco smoking. There is a possibility that

cigarette smoke may directly effect the normal flora of the mouth and thus permit a reselection.

Tobacco smoking has the effect by reducing the efficiency of cilia function and by causing the production of more viscous respiratory secretion tracheal intubation for prolonged periods in the ciliary ill bypasses the upper respiratory tract and provides a conduit for microbial access directly in to the lungs. The direct effects of smoking on the growth of many bacterial species isolated from humans are mostly unknown.

As it's a fact that smokers are more susceptible to multiple bacterial infections than are non-smokers. Such infections can be life-threatening and both active smokers as well as those exposed to second hand smoke toxins are at increased risk. This important relationship between smoking and ill-health may not be universally appreciated. Therefore, we set out to compare the presence of types of colonies in smokers and non smokers to summarize the evidence of relationship between tobacco smoking and the colonies found in smokers whose presence weakens the immune system, that may help explain the increased susceptibility to infectious disease in smokers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. SAMPLE COLLECTION

The sample (sputum) from both the smokers and non-smokers of age group between 20-38 years was collected. The volunteers were engineering student and workers involved in infrastructure construction. The volunteers are healthy individuals of both smokers and non-smokers. 15 samples from smokers and 15 from non-smokers was taken in sterile vials and wiped with absolute alcohol. Sample was collected in separate vials from different individuals in morning before brushing. As brushing kills some bacteria due to the antibacterial activity of toothpastes.

2. MICROBIAL CULTURE

Luria broth and YPD broth was prepared and 1:10 ml serial dilution was used to inoculate sputum sample and overnight culture was done at 37°C at 100 rpm in orbital shaker.

Sabour dextrose agar, Nutrient agar, Mannitol Agar and Luria Agar media (200 ml each) was made .4 sets of petriplates was prepared for each of the media and sputum sample was cultured on these plates by spread plate technique. Plates were kept in BOD incubator at 37°C overnight. Next day, growth was checked .Pure culture was done again for each colony on specific media using quadrant streaking.

3. MICROBIAL CHARACTERIZATION

Gram staining was done for all samples and microbes were characterized on the basis of their morphology, colour and observation as gram +ve or gram -ve.

RESULTS:

Table 1. Microbial profile in Smokers:

SMOKERS

S.No	Microbe	Total No of samples	No of samples showing microbe	Type of Sample
1	E.Coli	16	9	3 students & 6 workers
2	Streptococcus Aureus	16	11	5 students & 6 workers
3	Candida Albicans	16	10	1 student & 9 workers
4	No growth	16	1	student

Table 2. Microbial profile in Non-Smokers:

NON SMOKERS

Microbe	Total No of samples	No of samples showing microbe	Type of Sample
E.Coli	14	6	3 students & 3 workers
Streptococcus Aureus	14	7	2 students & 5 workers
Candida Albicans	14	4	4 workes
No growth	14	9	5 students & 5 workers

Table 3. Comparative Analysis of Microflora in Smokers Vs Nonsmokers:

S.No	Type of Microbe	SMOKERS	NON SMOKERS
1	E.Coli	9	6
2	Streptococcus Aureus	11	7
3	Candida Albicans	10	4
4	No growth	1	9

Fig 1. Comparison of bacteria and Fungus in Smokers & Nonsmokers samples

CONCLUSION

The prevalence and density of oral colonization was high in smokers as compared to non smokers. There was marginally higher prevalence of E.coli, Streptococcus aureus and Candida albicans in smokers sample as compared to nonsmokers. In view of the findings of the current work, additional studies are needed to examine the effect of tobacco smoking on oral & respiratory tract micro flora in a wider standardized population and further factors are recommended to be taken into consideration such as salivary composition, saliva flow, number of cigarettes smoked per day, occupational hazard, sputum size & microbial adhesion to epithelial cells.

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